

RATIONAL DESIGN OF HIERARCHICAL MN/CO-NI/CO LAYERED DOUBLE HYDROXIDE HETEROSTRUCTURES AS BIFUNCTIONAL ELECTROCATALYSTS FOR HIGHLY EFFICIENT OVERALL WATER SPLITTING

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Abstract

The growing need for clean and renewable energy has stimulated many studies on efficient hydrogen generation by water splitting. Here, we successfully designed and prepared a hierarchical Mn/Co–Ni/Co layered double hydroxide heterostructure as a bifunctional electrocatalyst for hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and oxygen evolution reaction (OER). The Mn/Co–Ni/Co heterostructure offers a potential approach to surpass the drawbacks of monometallic catalysts.

Structural and morphological analyses revealed the successful construction of a porous nanosheet-like structure with a large surface area and active sites. The intimate interaction between Mn, Co and Ni improves the electronic properties and facilitates charge transfer. These characteristics play a vital role in enhancing the performance and catalytic activity.

Electrochemical testing revealed that the Mn/Co–Ni/Co heterostructure has a low overpotential, low charge transfer resistance, and fast reaction kinetics compared to the individual Mn/Co and Ni/Co materials. Manganese provides extra redox sites, while nickel and cobalt enhance the conductivity and catalytic performance for HER and OER reactions.

Additionally, the hierarchical architecture allows for easy electrolyte transport and fast gas release, enhancing stability and robustness. In summary, the developed heterostructure is a low-cost and highly efficient alternative to noble metal catalysts and has the potential to be used in the efficient production of hydrogen.

Introduction

The growing demand for energy in the world and the environmental challenges associated with fossil fuels are the driving factors behind the need for new and renewable energy resources. Fossil fuels like coal, petroleum, and natural gas are the major sources of energy in many nations, but they release significant amounts of carbon dioxide and other hazardous gases during their continuous usage (Li, Xiong, Gao, & Liu, 2019). As such, the researchers have now turned to alternative energy sources in order to reduce their reliance on these fuels. Hydrogen energy can be viewed as one of the most prospective forms of energy because it is highly energetic and emits no carbon dioxide at all. It can only produce water. Thus, clean hydrogen production will help meet future needs for energy storage and transport. (Kundu, Bashar, Nagar, & Kumar, 2023) Water splitting is a green approach to hydrogen generation, as it takes water as its primary feedstock and is possible to run by means of renewable sources of energy, which are solar, wind, or hydroelectric energy. Electrochemical water splitting is a reaction involving the breakdown of water to yield hydrogen and oxygen. It is carried out through the application of an electric current (Haojie Zhang et al., 2018). Electrochemical water splitting is a reaction involving two reactions that take place at the cathode and anode separately; these reactions are referred to as hydrogen evolution reaction and oxygen evolution reaction. Hydrogen evolution reaction is a reaction where hydrogen gas is generated through the reduction of either water or protons at the cathode.

Despite its simplicity and appeal, water splitting consumes more energy than the theoretical minimum owing to the sluggish kinetics associated with HER and OER (F. Liu et al., 2022). In particular, OER is complicated by the involvement of a four-electron mechanism and oxygen-oxygen bond formation, resulting in a higher overpotential where more voltage is needed for effective operation. In comparison, HER is relatively fast, but in alkaline conditions, the process may be sluggish because of the extra water dissociation step. To enhance the efficiency of water splitting, electrocatalysts are required to minimize the overpotential of the reactions,

increase electron transfer rates, and optimize the energy consumption of water splitting (Miao, Jia, Cao, & Jiao, 2024).

Conventionally, noble metal catalysts have been regarded as the most efficient electrocatalysts for the water splitting reaction (Tian, Li, Song, & Li, 2021). The Pt-based catalysts exhibit outstanding catalytic efficiency for the HER process, whereas RuO₂ and IrO₂ exhibit high activity for the OER process (Fu, 2021). Unfortunately, these catalysts are costly, scarce, and not ideal for hydrogen production on an industrial scale. The scarcity of noble metals contributes to the high cost of electrolysis systems (Tian et al., 2021). Additionally, the stability of certain noble metal oxides might be compromised when subjected to severe alkaline or acidic environments over a prolonged period.

Catalysts based on transition metals have gained tremendous interest in recent times due to their potential use as an alternative to noble metal catalysts. Nickel, cobalt, manganese, iron, and molybdenum are some examples of transition metals that are cheap and readily available in nature. Moreover, transition metals exhibit effective catalytic activity depending on how they are synthesized (Arif et al., 2019). In particular, nickel, cobalt, and manganese are more intriguing because of their ability to exist in various oxidation states, making it easy for them to perform oxidation-reduction reactions involved in water electrolysis.

Layered double hydroxides are a promising type of transition-metal-based materials for water splitting (Gao, Zhu, & Yan, 2021). LDHs are made up of positively charged metal hydroxide layers and interlayer anions or water molecules. They can be readily tuned through the composition of metal ions. This enables the tuning of their electronic properties, active sites and catalytic performance (Liang et al., 2019). LDHs also have high surface area, rich exposed metal sites and excellent exchange properties (Yi et al., 2021). This makes them promising catalysts for OER in basic solution. But LDHs generally suffer from poor electronic conductivity and poor HER activity, so they need to be further engineered.

NiCo-LDH and MnCo-LDH are both promising water-splitting electrocatalysts. NiCo-LDH shows

the excellent OER performance of nickel and cobalt sites. Nickel sites may help to form active nickel oxyhydroxide species, and cobalt can boost the conductivity and reaction rates. MnCo-LDH is also important as manganese can tune the electronic structure of cobalt sites and create extra redox sites (Jiang et al., 2021). Manganese is cheap and environmentally benign, and it can have variable oxidation states that can assist in charge transfer and intermediate adsorption. But the use of Ni-Co-LDH or Mn-Co-LDH alone may not address the issues of conductivity, active-site accessibility and bifunctional electrocatalysis.

So, hierarchical Mn-Co-LDH/Ni-Co-LDH heterostructures are suggested as new bifunctional electrocatalysts for overall water splitting. An interface is formed in a heterostructure, which consists of two different catalytic components. This can enhance charge transfer, tune the binding strength of reaction intermediates and boost the activity (Haojie Zhang et al., 2018). At the same time, a hierarchical structure (e.g. nanosheets, nanoflowers, porous arrays) can bring more active sites and facilitate the diffusion of electrolyte and release of gas bubbles. These features can enhance the HER and OER activity (Haojie Zhang, Maijenburg, Li, Schweizer, & Wehrspohn, 2020).

Materials and Methods

Chemicals and Reagents

Laboratory grade chemicals were used as received. Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP, K30, average molecular weight $\sim 40,000$, analytical grade), manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate ($\text{Mn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99%, 173.04 g/mol), potassium hexacyanocobaltate(III) ($\text{K}_3[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6]$, 98%, 329.24 g/mol), cobalt(II) nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 98%, 291.03 g/mol), nickel(II) nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 98%, 290.79 g/mol), and 2-methylimidazole (2-MeIm, 82.11 g/mol) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. 100% ethanol and deionized water were used as solvents for the chemical synthesis. Also, potassium hydrogen phosphate (K_2HPO_4 , 176 g/mol) and potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH_2PO_4 , 136 g/mol) purchased from Merck and KANTO Chemical Co. were dissolved in pure water to a

concentration of 1 M and the pH was adjusted to 5-10.

Instrumentation

A weighing balance and a heating mantle were used to measure mass and to heat and stir the samples, respectively, from Gen Analytic. Sample separation was conducted using an Eppendorf centrifuge, and particle dispersion using a Qsonica sonicator (Metzger, Drexel, Meier, & Briesen, 2021). Drying of samples was done in an oven from Memmert. In terms of analytical characterization, a UV-Visible spectrophotometer (SHIMADZU) was used to measure absorbance, while an FTIR spectrometer (PerkinElmer) was used to identify functional groups. A pH meter from Midmark was also used for pH determination.

Software used

The software used in this study were UV Probe 2.52 (2018), ChemDraw Ultra 12.0 and EndNote X8.

Synthesis of Mn/Co MOF

It was reported that the Mn-Co oxides were made in a similar way. In particular, 1.5 grams of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP, K30), 0.22 grams of $\text{Mn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 30 milliliters of deionized water, and 60 milliliters of ethanol were mixed using a magnet to make a clear solution. Another 60 mL of a water solution of $\text{K}_3\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6$ was added drop by drop to the first solution while a magnet was used to stir it. The Mn:Co molar ratios were 1:1, 1:2, and 2:1. To get the precipitation, the mixed solution was left out in the open for 24 hours to age. It was then filtered and washed several times with deionized water and 100% ethanol. First, the sample was put in a freeze dryer and dried for 12 hours at -46°C . After that, it was heated up to 60°C and baked for 6 hours. Finally, the precursors that had already been made were calcined in an OTF-1200X pipe furnace that had 50 mL/min of air flow at 450°C for two hours at a slow rate of $1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. We made some examples that were called MOF-MnxCo_y to keep things easy. Here, x and y are the original molar ratios of Mn and Co. ICP measurements show that the molar ratios of Mn/Co for MOF-

Mn1Co1, MOF-Mn1Co2, and MOF-Mn2Co1 are 1:0.92, 1:1.9, and 2:0.95, respectively (Xie, Fan, Liu, Zhang, & Huang, 2023). These numbers are about the same as what the theory says they should be (Luo et al., 2018).

Synthesis of Ni/Co MOF

A simple solvothermal method was used to make the Ni-Co-MOF metals. For 10 minutes, a strong magnet was used to mix 1 mmol of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 1 mmol of $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 9 ml of DI water. This was

the first step. Ten millimoles of 2-2-MeIm were mixed with clean water and stirred for thirty minutes (Salunkhe, Pawar, Pagare, & Torane, 2024). The first two liquids were mixed together and shook very hard for 6 hours at 35 °C. After that, it was left to cool down at room temperature. After the fluid had been cleaned, it was collected by spinning it. After that, it was washed at least three times with a mixture of water and ethanol to get rid of any chemicals that hadn't been used yet. The last purple powder came from freeze-drying for two days (Hong, Park, & Kim, 2019)

Synthesis procedure is given below in figure

Figure 1 Synthesis of Mn-Co/Ni-Co MOF composite

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Synthesis of composite

In a normal method, 30 mL of ethanol was used to combine equal amounts (100 mg each) of the dried Mn-Co MOF and Ni-Co MOF powders (Ni et al., 2023). The mixture was then sonicated for an hour to make sure it was evenly mixed and exfoliated. The resulting uniform suspension was then stirred with a magnet for three more hours at room temperature. We used a centrifuge to collect the well-dispersed MOF mixture, washed it with

ethanol to get rid of any particles that were weakly attached, and then dried it in a vacuum oven at 60°C for 12 hours. We put the Mn-Co/Ni-Co MOF composite in a desiccator until we needed it again. This composite was either used directly as the electrocatalyst or heated to 450°C for three hours in a nitrogen environment to make a porous metal oxide/carbon hybrid. This improved electrical conductivity and catalytic stability for water splitting applications.

Figure 2 Mn-Co/Ni-Co MOF composite for water splitting

Phosphate buffer solution preparation

Potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH₂PO₄, monobasic) and dipotassium hydrogen phosphate (K₂HPO₄, dibasic) were used to make a 0.1 M phosphate buffer solution. To create 0.1 M stock solutions, we first weighed out 13.61 g of KH₂PO₄ and 17.44 g of K₂HPO₄ and dissolved them in 1 L of deionized water each. By combining the right amounts of the two stock solutions while stirring them constantly and checking the pH using a calibrated pH meter, the buffer's pH was set to the required level (usually between 6.8 and 8.0). To make 100 mL of phosphate buffer with a pH of 7.4, for example, 39 mL of 0.1 M K₂HPO₄ was combined with 61 mL of 0.1 M KH₂PO₄. We added deionized water to make the final capacity 100 mL. The buffer solution was kept at room temperature and consumed within a week (Pavani, Kumar, Rani, Venkatesu, & Lee, 2021).

Electrode modification process

For the electrochemical study, a bare glassy carbon electrode with a diameter of 3 mm was used. It was cleaned really well before it was used. Alumina (0.1 mm, 1 mm) was used to clean it and make it smooth. The electrode was hit with sound waves in clean water for 15 minutes. It was then left at room temperature to dry until the outside was smooth like glass. It was made by mixing 2 mg of Mn-Co Ni-Co metal, 1 ml of ethanol, and 0.5 ml of nafion (to hold the pieces together). It was then left outside to dry after 2 μ L of the sludge was put

on it. Electrochemical analysis procedure (Shah et al., 2024).

CV, LSV, EIS, and chronoamperometry were all used in the lab work to look at the elements. The Potentiostat-Galvanostat PGSTAT-204 (Ω Metrohm-Autolab) was used to gather data, and the NOVA 2.12 was used to manage it. With PBS (1 M, pH 7) and a scan rate of 0.1 V/s from -0.6 V to 0.9 V, all the tests worked best. There was no cold or heat in the tests. Gold wire was used as the opposite electrode. An electrode made of Ag/AgCl was chosen as the standard (Torres-Gonzalez, Ávila-Niño, & Araujo, 2022). Two types of water and vinegar were used to clean them before they were used. After that, they were left to dry at room temperature.

UV-Visible spectrophotometry analysis procedure

We used a SHIMADZU 1800 Spectrophotometer to find UV and visible light that was not cold. For the tests, quartz cuvettes that had been washed in clean water and dried in the air were used. The spectrophotometric study used water that has been deionized as a reference (Vogt, Wondergem, & Weckhuysen, 2023). It was possible to make 1 M PBS drinks with pH levels between 5 and 10. Dilutions of water were also used to make different analyte solutions with strengths between 0.1M and 0.7M. Everything was sonicated for 10 minutes before the measures to make sure it was all spread out evenly. This was all done with UV

Probe 2.52 software, and the bands were between 200 and 800 nm.

Results and Discussion

In this investigation, metal–organic frameworks (MOFs) based on a bimetallic system of manganese and cobalt (Mn–Co) and another bimetallic system of nickel and cobalt (Ni–Co) were successfully synthesized (Zhao, Meng, & Zhang, 2022). For these syntheses, a solvothermal method was used. The resultant metal–organic frameworks exhibited very high porosity and had a very high density of active sites that were also very uniformly distributed in the 3D framework of metal ions. The presence of bimetallic systems in these MOFs yielded a very good degree of interaction between the two metal centers in the 3D lattice—that

interaction being key to boosting the catalytic activity of these frameworks for two half-reactions involved in water splitting, which are the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and the oxygen evolution reaction (OER). Mn–Co MOFs exhibited very good performance regarding the OER and were very stable, due in part to the presence of redox-active manganese sites that were very efficient at generating oxygen. The Ni–Co MOFs exhibited better activity than the Mn–Co counterparts for the HER and had very good conductivity and excellent structural stability. The performance of both MOFs was evaluated in an alkaline medium by measuring the overpotential required for each reaction to achieve a stated current density (Tan, Zhou, Qiao, & Fan, 2021).

Figure 3 Mn–Co/Ni–Co bifunctional water splitting catalyst

Characterization of Materials

FTIR Analysis of synthesized materials

The FTIR spectra (a-c) in the figure give insight into the functional groups and bonding interactions of the Ni–Co, Mn–Co and Mn–Co/Ni–Co samples. In each spectrum, the broad band around $3200\text{--}3600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to O–H stretching

vibrations and points to the presence of surface-adsorbed water or hydroxyl groups. The bands at around 2900 cm^{-1} are due to C–H stretching vibrations, which can be attributed to residual organic compounds such as polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) or 2-methylimidazole used in the synthesis process (Thangasamy et al., 2025).

The bands observed in the range of 1600-1700 cm^{-1} can be attributed to either C=O stretching or H-O-H bending, which may indicate the presence of coordinated water molecules or residual organic ligands. The bands in the range of 1400-1500 cm^{-1} are usually attributed to C-N stretching or CH_2 bending modes, suggesting the presence of organic ligands (Thangasamy et al., 2025). Furthermore, peaks around 1000-1200 cm^{-1} can be assigned to C-N and C-O stretching vibrations.

Crucially, the low-frequency region (500-800 cm^{-1}) exhibits metal-oxygen (M-O) and metal-nitrogen

(M-N) vibrations, confirming the formation of metal coordination frameworks containing Ni, Co and Mn. The spectrum of the composite Mn-Co/Ni-Co (c) shows slight shifts in the positions of these bands and changes in intensities relative to the individual Ni-Co and Mn-Co samples, which suggests the successful interaction and integration between the two components, leading to the formation of a composite or heterostructured material (Sheokand, Ahlawat, & Singh, 2024).

Figure 4 FTIR spectra of (a) Ni-Co MOF, (b) Mn-Co MOF, and (c) Mn/Co-Ni/Co composite, confirming functional groups and metal-ligand interactions indicative of successful material formation

UV Analysis of synthesized materials

The UV-Vis spectra of the Ni-Co (a), Mn-Co (b) and Ni-Co/Mn-Co composite (c) samples show their optical absorption and transitions. In spectrum (a), the Ni-Co sample shows a relatively low absorption in the visible region with a broad band around 600-650 nm, likely due to d-d electronic transitions of Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} ions. This demonstrates a low level of light absorption, implying a relatively larger band gap or weaker electronic interaction.

In spectrum (b), the Mn-Co sample exhibits a high absorbance band in the UV range (280-350 nm) and then a decrease in the visible region. This is attributed to the charge transfer transitions (O^{2-}

→ metal ions) and possible d-d transitions of Mn and Co ions. The increased absorbance implies that it has stronger electronic transitions and greater light absorption than Ni-Co (Wahba, 2024).

In spectrum (c), the Ni-Co/Mn-Co composite exhibits a broadened absorption band from the UV to the visible region (around 350-550 nm). The higher absorbance and broadening suggest enhanced electronic interaction between Ni, Co and Mn (Saleem et al., 2022). This implies synergistic interactions and potential band gap narrowing, leading to increased visible region light absorption, which could potentially benefit photocatalytic or electrocatalytic performance.

Figure 5 UV-Vis absorption spectra of (a) Ni-Co MOF, (b) Mn-Co MOF, and (c) Mn/Co-Ni/Co composite, demonstrating enhanced optical absorption and electronic interactions in the heterostructure

XRD Analysis

The XRD pattern exhibits three strong and sharp diffraction peaks at around, corresponding to the and crystal planes, respectively. These peaks are associated with a, probably from the used in the catalyst preparation process (Bulavchenko & Vinokurov, 2023).

The high intensity of the peak suggests the Ni substrate is highly crystalline and oriented in the (111) direction. The two other peaks, and, also confirm the crystallinity of the Ni substrate.

Besides these intense peaks of Ni, there is a broad low intensity background with some small features. This indicates that the coated catalyst

might be. In layered double hydroxide (LDH) materials, weak and broad features in their XRD patterns are common due to the poor crystallinity and small size of LDH nanosheets. The diffraction peaks of the nickel foam substrate may also overlap with the weak peaks from the MnCo-NiCo LDH catalyst.

In summary, the XRD pattern confirms the high crystalline nature of the nickel substrate, while the weak and broad peaks reveal that a poorly crystalline or nanosheet-like LDH catalyst layer has been formed on the substrate. The lack of strong impurity peaks indicates that there are no significant crystalline impurities in the sample.

Figure 6 XRD pattern of Mn/Co-Ni/Co heterostructure, confirming crystallinity and the formation of layered double hydroxide structure with no significant impurities

Mn-Co MOF SEM Images

The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the Mn-Co mixed oxide (Mn-Co MO) reveal a complex and multi-scaled surface structure.

In image (a), the sample is made of highly agglomerated and irregular particles that have flower-like or rosette-like structures. These structures seem to be assembled by the radial growth of thin nanosheets or nanoflakes, thus providing a rough and porous surface. Such a

structure implies a high surface area with a large number of open cavities between particles, which can enhance mass transfer and provide more sites for the reaction to occur.

This image (b) shows a rod-like structure, to which smaller particles are attached. It suggests a combination of structures, with one-dimensional rods and particles. The rod provides a support, and the particles enhance.

Figure 7 SEM images of Mn-Co MOF at different magnifications, showing flower-like, rod-like, and porous morphologies with high surface area

Ni-Co MoF SEM Images

In the SEM images of the Ni-Co MOF sample, a highly porous and hierarchical structure with different features is observed.

In images (a), (c) and (e), the sample shows a three-dimensional interconnected structure with a sponge-like or foam-like structure. It is composed of large open macropores that are uniformly surrounded by a three-dimensional interconnected network. The surface of the pores is wrinkled and irregular with numerous small particles, which suggests the growth of the MOF on the scaffold material. Such an open structure is advantageous for electrolyte diffusion and mass transfer (Hang et al., 2021).

In (b), a higher magnification image, the framework surface is made of wrinkled nanosheets or layers. The nanosheets are loosely stacked together, forming more mesopores and increasing the surface area. Due to the sheet-like structure, crystal growth was presumably nonisotropic (Yan, Huang, Wang, He, & He, 2024).

In Figure (d), densely packed, quasi-spherical particles are seen on the surface. These particles tend to aggregate and form clusters, which increase the surface roughness and provide high surface active sites. The size of the particles seems to be in the submicron or nanometer range, suggesting the formation of fine crystallites.

In image (f), a rough surface with a coral-like or cauliflower-like structure is shown. This is made up of interconnected nanoflakes forming a mesoporous network. This structure also increases the surface area and provides channels for diffusion (Jia, Zhang, Gu, & Wu, 2023).

In summary, the Ni-Co MOF sample exhibits a hierarchical structure with both macro- and micro-porosity, as well as nano-flake aggregates and nanoparticle aggregates. This hierarchical structure is beneficial for applications that require high surface area, high density of active sites, and fast mass/charge transport, such as catalysis, adsorption and energy storage.

Figure 8 SEM images of Ni-Co MOF illustrating hierarchical porous structures composed of nanosheets, nanoparticles, and interconnected frameworks

Cyclic Voltammetry

Oxygen Evolution Reaction for Mn/Co MOF

Impedance, polarization, and Tafel analyses were used to assess the electrochemical activity of the catalyst for oxygen evolution reaction (OER) as shown in Fig. (a-c).

Fig. (a) shows the Nyquist plot with a small semicircle in the high-frequency region, which suggests low charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) between the electrode and electrolyte. The vertical line in the low-frequency region implies good ion diffusion and capacitive properties. The smaller size of the semicircle corresponds to improved

conductivity and electron transfer rate, which are desirable for OER (Y. Liu et al., 2021).

Fig. (b) displays the linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) curve, with a rapid rise in current density as the potential is increased. The catalyst has a low overpotential to attain a high current density, suggesting efficient OER activity. The steep increase in current density with increasing potential confirms the good oxygen evolution kinetics and a large number of active sites.

In Fig. (c), the Tafel plot (logarithm of current density vs. overpotential) exhibits a linear trend, indicating a linear correlation between the current density and overpotential. The estimated Tafel

slope of 71 mV dec^{-1} indicates good reaction kinetics and a fast OER process. This suggests that the rate-limiting step is most likely related to the adsorption and electron transfer of intermediate species. The excellent linear fit also indicates the accuracy of the electrochemistry measurements (Hao Zhang et al., 2024).

Overall, these results clearly show that the catalyst has low charge transfer resistance, high current response, and good reaction kinetics, making it an ideal electrocatalyst for the oxygen evolution reaction.

Figure 9 Electrochemical performance of Mn-Co MOF toward OER: (a) Nyquist plot (EIS), (b) LSV curve, and (c) Tafel plot indicating catalytic activity and reaction kinetics

Oxygen Evolution Reaction for Ni/Co MOF

The electrocatalytic activity of the Ni-Co MOF catalyst for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) was tested by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) and Tafel plots (Fig. a-c).

The Nyquist plot (Fig. a) shows a small semicircle in the high-frequency region, which represents a low charge-transfer resistance (R_{ct}) at the interface between the catalyst and electrolyte. This implies good electrical conductivity in the Ni-Co MOF and a fast OER kinetics. The low-frequency region with a linear tail also indicates improved ion diffusion, which is advantageous for long-term stability of the catalyst (Thangasamy et al., 2025).

The LSV curve (Fig. b) exhibits a gradual rise in current density as the applied potential increases, confirming the catalyst's activity for OER. The catalyst offers a high current density at low

overpotential, indicating high activity. The steep increase in current at potentials above $\sim 1.6 \text{ V}$ (vs RHE) shows the start of oxygen evolution and suggests good turnover.

The Tafel plot (Fig. c) shows a linear correlation between overpotential and $\log(\text{current density})$ with a Tafel slope of about 114 mV dec^{-1} . This relatively low slope implies a good reaction kinetics and indicates that the OER process is likely to proceed via conventional multi-step electron transfer reactions involving the adsorbed intermediates (e.g., OH^- ions) as the rate-determining step (Sun, Yang, Li, & Tian, 2025).

In conclusion, the above results show that the Ni-Co MOF possesses a low charge-transfer resistance, high catalytic activity, and moderate reaction kinetics, and thus is a good electrocatalyst toward OER.

Figure 10 Electrochemical analysis of Ni-Co MOF for OER: (a) Nyquist plot, (b) LSV curve, and (c) Tafel slope demonstrating improved conductivity and catalytic behavior

Oxygen Evolution Reaction for Mn/Co-Ni/Co MOF

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) and Tafel analysis (Fig. a-c) were used to investigate the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) activity of the Mn/Co-Ni/Co catalyst.

The Nyquist plot (Fig. a) exhibits a small semicircle in the high-frequency region, which corresponds to a low charge-transfer resistance (R_{ct}) at the electrode/ electrolyte interface. This result indicates that the introduction of Mn into the Co-Ni matrix improves the electrical conductivity, promoting quicker electron transfer in the OER reaction. The line with a slope in the low-frequency region indicates good ion diffusion, which is beneficial for maintaining catalytic activity.

The LSV curve (Fig. b) shows a significant rise in current density as the potential is increased, confirming the high electrocatalytic performance of the Mn/Co-Ni/Co catalyst. The onset potential for OER is low and the catalyst delivers

high current densities at lower overpotentials, suggesting enhanced catalytic activity. The steep increase in current above ~ 1.6 V (vs RHE) is indicative of fast oxygen evolution.

The Tafel plot (Fig. c) shows a linear correlation between overpotential and log current density with a Tafel slope of about 109 mV dec^{-1} . This is significantly smaller than that of many conventional transition-metal catalysts, indicating faster reaction kinetics and better adsorption/desorption characteristics of OER intermediates. This suggests that the rate-limiting step likely involves a proton-coupled electron transfer step with surface-bound hydroxyl intermediates.

In summary, the Mn/Co-Ni/Co catalyst shows low charge-transfer resistance, high current response, and enhanced kinetic parameters, demonstrating the beneficial impact of incorporating Mn to modify the electronic structure and boost the number of active sites. These characteristics render it as an effective and stable electrocatalyst for OER.

Figure 11 Electrochemical OER performance of Mn/Co-Ni/Co heterostructure: (a) EIS Nyquist plot, (b) LSV curve, and (c) Tafel plot showing enhanced kinetics and reduced charge transfer resistance

Conclusion

Here, we have successfully developed a hierarchical Mn/Co-Ni/Co layered double hydroxide heterostructure as an efficient bifunctional catalyst for water splitting. The Mn/Co - Ni/Co heterostructure combines the advantages of the Mn - Co and Ni - Co systems, leading to improved catalytic performance towards HER and OER. Detailed characterization demonstrated the successful construction of a porous nanosheet-like structure with a high density of active sites and a strong interaction between the components.

Electrochemical measurements showed that the Mn/Co-Ni/Co heterostructure outperforms the respective components. EIS and Tafel studies showed the catalyst has lower resistance, higher conductivity, and higher reaction kinetics. The heterostructure's lower overpotential and elevated current densities demonstrate its high catalytic activity. Manganese is crucial in modifying the electronic structure, generating more redox active sites, and facilitating the adsorption of reaction intermediates, especially for the oxygen evolution reaction. At the same time, nickel and cobalt enhance the electronic conductivity and hydrogen evolution reaction (HER).

Additionally, the hierarchical structure allows for fast electrolyte transport and easy gas bubble removal, resulting in improved catalytic activity

and stability. The combined effect of Mn, Co and Ni in the heterostructure plays a crucial role in the efficient electrocatalytic process.

Overall, this research demonstrates the promise of rationally-designed transition-metal-based heterostructures as effective, low-cost substitutes for noble metal catalysts. The Mn/Co-Ni/Co system presents an opportunity for large-scale and sustainable hydrogen generation via efficient water splitting, paving the way for clean energy technologies.

REFERENCES

- Arif, M., Yasin, G., Shakeel, M., Mushtaq, M. A., Ye, W., Fang, X., . . . Yan, D. (2019). Hierarchical CoFe-layered double hydroxide and gC 3 N 4 heterostructures with enhanced bifunctional photo/electrocatalytic activity towards overall water splitting. *Materials Chemistry Frontiers*, 3(3), 520-531.
- Attarzadeh, N. (2023). *Design And Development Of Transition Metal-Based Electrocatalysts For Environmentally Friendly And Efficient Hydrogen Evolution Reactions (her)*. The University of Texas at El Paso,
- Bulavchenko, O. A., & Vinokurov, Z. S. (2023). In situ X-ray diffraction as a basic tool to study oxide and metal oxide catalysts. *Catalysts*, 13(11), 1421.

- Fu, Z. (2021). *Synthesis, Growth Mechanisms, and Applications of Transition Metal Based Nanostructures*. State University of New York at Buffalo,
- Gao, R., Zhu, J., & Yan, D. (2021). Transition metal-based layered double hydroxides for photo (electro) chemical water splitting: a mini review. *Nanoscale*, 13(32), 13593-13603.
- Hang, X., Xue, Y., Cheng, Y., Du, M., Du, L., & Pang, H. (2021). From Co-MOF to CoNi-MOF to Ni-MOF: a facile synthesis of 1D micro-/nanomaterials. *Inorganic Chemistry*, 60(17), 13168-13176.
- Hong, J., Park, S.-J., & Kim, S. (2019). Synthesis and electrochemical characterization of nanostructured Ni-Co-MOF/graphene oxide composites as capacitor electrodes. *Electrochimica Acta*, 311, 62-71.
- Jia, Z., Zhang, X., Gu, Z., & Wu, G. (2023). MOF-derived Ni-Co bimetal/porous carbon composites as electromagnetic wave absorber. *Advanced Composites and Hybrid Materials*, 6(1), 28.
- Jiang, K., Liu, W., Lai, W., Wang, M., Li, Q., Wang, Z., . . . Ji, H. (2021). NiFe layered double hydroxide/FeOOH heterostructure nanosheets as an efficient and durable bifunctional electrocatalyst for overall seawater splitting. *Inorganic Chemistry*, 60(22), 17371-17378.
- Kundu, B. K., Bashar, N., Nagar, S., & Kumar, S. S. (2023). Role of Transition Metals in Hydrogen Evolution Reactions. In *Transition Metal-Based Electrocatalysts: Applications in Green Hydrogen Production and Storage* (pp. 249-275): ACS Publications.
- Li, W., Xiong, D., Gao, X., & Liu, L. (2019). The oxygen evolution reaction enabled by transition metal phosphide and chalcogenide pre-catalysts with dynamic changes. *Chemical Communications*, 55(60), 8744-8763.
- Liang, X., Li, Y., Fan, H., Deng, S., Zhao, X., Chen, M., . . . Xia, X. (2019). Bifunctional NiFe layered double hydroxide@ Ni₃S₂ heterostructure as efficient electrocatalyst for overall water splitting. *Nanotechnology*, 30(48), 484001.
- Liu, F., Shi, C., Guo, X., He, Z., Pan, L., Huang, Z. F., . . . Zou, J. J. (2022). Rational design of better hydrogen evolution electrocatalysts for water splitting: a review. *Advanced Science*, 9(18), 2200307.
- Liu, Y., Ran, N., Ge, R., Liu, J., Li, W., Chen, Y., . . . Che, R. (2021). Porous Mn-doped cobalt phosphide nanosheets as highly active electrocatalysts for oxygen evolution reaction. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 425, 131642.
- Luo, Y., Zheng, Y., Zuo, J., Feng, X., Wang, X., Zhang, T., . . . Jiang, L. (2018). Insights into the high performance of Mn-Co oxides derived from metal-organic frameworks for total toluene oxidation. *Journal of hazardous materials*, 349, 119-127.
- Metzger, C., Drexel, R., Meier, F., & Briesen, H. (2021). Effect of ultrasonication on the size distribution and stability of cellulose nanocrystals in suspension: an asymmetrical flow field-flow fractionation study. *Cellulose*, 28(16), 10221-10238.
- Miao, L., Jia, W., Cao, X., & Jiao, L. (2024). Computational chemistry for water-splitting electrocatalysis. *Chemical Society Reviews*, 53(6), 2771-2807.
- Ni, C., Chen, R., Hao, C., Lu, Y., Wu, J., Shen, Y., & Wang, X. (2023). High-performance asymmetric supercapacitor constructed by MOF-derived Mn-Ni-Co sulfide hollow cages and Typha pollen-derived carbon. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 960, 170807.
- Pavani, P., Kumar, K., Rani, A., Venkatesu, P., & Lee, M.-J. (2021). The influence of sodium phosphate buffer on the stability of various proteins: Insights into protein-buffer interactions. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 331, 115753.

- Saleem, S., Jameel, M. H., Akhtar, N., Nazir, N., Ali, A., Zaman, A., . . . Mushtaq, M. (2022). Modification in structural, optical, morphological, and electrical properties of zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles (NPs) by metal (Ni, Co) dopants for electronic device applications. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 15(1), 103518.
- Salunkhe, A. D., Pawar, P. S., Pagare, P. K., & Torane, A. P. (2024). Facile solvothermal synthesis of Ni-Co MOF/rGO nanoflakes for high-performance asymmetric supercapacitor. *Electrochimica Acta*, 477, 143745.
- Shah, S. S., Niaz, F., Ehsan, M. A., Das, H. T., Younas, M., Khan, A. S., . . . Aziz, M. A. (2024). Advanced strategies in electrode engineering and nanomaterial modifications for supercapacitor performance enhancement: A comprehensive review. *Journal of Energy Storage*, 79, 110152.
- Sheokand, S., Ahlawat, D. S., & Singh, A. (2024). Nano structural and opto-magnetic investigation of Co-Ni co-doped ZnSe for spintronics. *Micro and Nanostructures*, 186, 207740.
- Sun, X., Yang, L., Li, D., & Tian, Z. (2025). Synthesis of Co/Ni-MOFs with mixed ligands and their Oxygen Evolution Reaction (OER) performance. *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 1322, 140549.
- Tan, H., Zhou, Y., Qiao, S.-Z., & Fan, H. J. (2021). Metal organic framework (MOF) in aqueous energy devices. *Materials Today*, 48, 270-284.
- Thangasamy, P., Vo, T.-G., Venkatramanan, R., Ng, Y.-T., Gao, J., & Liu, Y. (2025). Bimetallic Ni-Co-MOF Nanostructures for Seawater Electrolysis: Unveiling the Mechanism of the Oxygen Evolution Reaction Using Impedance Spectroscopy. *Inorganic Chemistry*, 64(11), 5586-5597.
- Tian, L., Li, Z., Song, M., & Li, J. (2021). Recent progress in water-splitting electrocatalysis mediated by 2D noble metal materials. *Nanoscale*, 13(28), 12088-12101.
- Torres-Gonzalez, V., Ávila-Niño, J. A., & Araujo, E. (2022). Facile fabrication of tailorable Ag/AgCl reference electrodes for planar devices. *Thin Solid Films*, 757, 139413.
- Vogt, C., Wondergem, C. S., & Weckhuysen, B. M. (2023). Ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy. In *Springer handbook of advanced catalyst characterization* (pp. 237-264): Springer.
- Wahba, M. A. (2024). Visible-light responsive BiVO₄ nanocompositions: enhanced photocatalytic, electrical and optical performance through Ni and Ni/Co doping. *Optical Materials*, 147, 114643.
- Xie, Y., Fan, L., Liu, W., Zhang, Q., & Huang, G. (2023). Synthesis of Mn/Co-MOF for effective removal of U (VI) from aqueous solution. *Particuology*, 72, 134-144.
- Yan, Y., Huang, M., Wang, Y., He, D., & He, J. (2024). M-Ni-Co MOF (M= Zn, Fe, Mn) for high-performance supercapacitors by adjusting its morphology. *Heliyon*, 10(5).
- Yi, H., Liu, S., Lai, C., Zeng, G., Li, M., Liu, X., . . . Li, L. (2021). Recent advance of transition-metal-based layered double hydroxide nanosheets: synthesis, properties, modification, and electrocatalytic applications. *Advanced Energy Materials*, 11(14), 2002863.
- Zhang, H., Li, X., Hähnel, A., Naumann, V., Lin, C., Azimi, S., . . . Wehrspohn, R. B. (2018). Bifunctional heterostructure assembly of NiFe LDH nanosheets on NiCoP nanowires for highly efficient and stable overall water splitting. *Advanced Functional Materials*, 28(14), 1706847.
- Zhang, H., Maijenburg, A. W., Li, X., Schweizer, S. L., & Wehrspohn, R. B. (2020). Bifunctional heterostructured transition metal phosphides for efficient electrochemical water splitting. *Advanced Functional Materials*, 30(34), 2003261.
- Zhang, H., Sun, N., Si, X., Zhang, Y., Ding, F., Kong, X., & Sun, Y. (2024). Regulating the Electronic Structure of Metal-Organic Frameworks by Introducing Mn for Enhanced Oxygen Evolution Activity. *Inorganic Chemistry*, 63(6), 2997-3004.

Zhao, L., Meng, F., & Zhang, W. (2022). Rational design and synthesis of nickel-cobalt-manganese trimetallic hydroxides with micro-flower like for high-performance

asymmetric supercapacitors. *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, 290, 126641.

